

UK Government Intellectual Property Office

Consultation on Copyright and Artificial Intelligence

Response by Edinburgh College of Art,
University of Edinburgh

February 2025

Information Commissioner's Officer Consultation on Copyright and Artificial Intelligence

Response by Edinburgh College of Art¹, University of Edinburgh

Submission prepared by:

- Nicola Osborne, Manager of the Institute for Design Informatics², Edinburgh College of Art; Co-I CoSTAR Realtime Lab³; Co-Investigator (Co-I) UKRI AI CDT in Responsible and Trustworthy in-the-world Natural Language Processing⁴; Creative Informatics⁵ (2018-24) programme manager and Creative AI Demonstrator⁶ (2023-4) lead.
- Caroline Parkinson, Director of Creative/ Sector Engagement Manager – Creative Industries, Edinburgh Futures Institute⁷, University of Edinburgh
- Professor Melissa Terras, Professor of Digital Cultural Heritage, Edinburgh College of Art, University of Edinburgh; Principal Investigator Creative Informatics (2022-4); Co-I CoSTAR Realtime Lab; Co-I CoSTAR Foresight Lab⁸; Co-I UKRI AI CDT in Responsible and Trustworthy in-the-world Natural Language Processing; Co-I XRNetwork+⁹; Co-I Fixing the Future – The Right to Repair and Equal-IoT¹⁰; Scholarly Director, READ-COOP SCE¹¹.
- Professor Juan Cruz, Principal, Edinburgh College of Art, University of Edinburgh

Cover credits: Image of Ben Cantil of DataMind Audio¹² performing under his stage name, Encanti, at the Creative Informatics Creative AI Demonstrator event 'Exploring the Potential for Creative AI Showcase' held at Platform, Glasgow, on 28th November 2023. Image credit: Chris Scott. Cantil's performance used DataMind Audio's 'Combobulator' software, which allows musicians and music producers to use ethical generative AI models or 'Artist's Brains' in their music making. These models are trained on specific named musician and music producer data, with their full permission and a business model that ensured that their contribution is credited and paid for through shared revenue. DataMind Audio's Combobulator is an exemplar of a creator-led product using emerging generative AI technology and an innovative business model which respects the copyright and livelihoods of the creatives whose training data powers the product.

¹ <https://www.eca.ed.ac.uk/>

² <https://www.designinformatics.org/>

³ <https://www.costarnetwork.co.uk/labs/realtimelab>

⁴ <https://www.responsiblenlp.org/>

⁵ <https://creativeinformatics.org/>

⁶ <https://creativeinformatics.org/programme/creative-ai-demonstrator-project/>

⁷ <https://efi.ed.ac.uk/>

⁸ <https://www.costarnetwork.co.uk/labs/foresightlab>

⁹ <https://xrstories.co.uk/about/networkplus/>

¹⁰ <https://ftf.wp.horizon.ac.uk/>

¹¹ <https://readcoop.org/>

¹² <https://datamindaudio.ai/>

Introduction

This document reflects the response provided by Edinburgh College of Art to the UK Government Information Commissioner's Officer Consultation on Copyright and Artificial Intelligence (AI)¹³, which ran from 17th December 2024 until 25th February 2025.

Our response was submitted through the formal consultation portal¹⁴, which included all questions. We did not choose to respond to all questions in the consultation, but we include the full list of questions in the Appendix for reference.

Our response draws on expertise at Edinburgh College of Art in undertaking leading research in art, design and creative industries, and in training the next generation artists and creators through undergraduate and postgraduate programmes. We also draw on substantial expertise in working in partnership with the creative industries on ambitious large scale creative data and technology innovation programmes, particularly:

- Creative Informatics (2018-2024) and specifically the Creative AI Demonstrator (2023-4), funded by AHRC (the Arts and Humanities Research Council), the Data Driven Innovation Programme of the Edinburgh City Region Deal, Scottish Funding Council (SFC), and DCMS (the Department of Culture, Media & Sport).
- CoSTAR Realtime Lab (2023-), funded through UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Infrastructure Fund and delivered by the AHRC.
- ekip: European Cultural and Creative Sectors and Industries Policy Platform (2023-), funded by the European Commission, with ECA participation supported under the UKRI Horizon Europe Guarantee Scheme.

Summary

The consultation sought views on how the government can ensure the UK's legal framework for AI and copyright supports the UK creative industries and AI sector together. In particular, the consultation sought views on four identified options (referred to throughout our response) with the Government's preference noted as 'Option 3':

- Option 0: Do nothing: Copyright and related laws remain as they are.
- Option 1: Strengthen copyright requiring licensing in all cases
- Option 2: A broad data mining exception
- Option 3: A data mining exception which allows right holders to reserve their rights, underpinned by supporting measures on transparency

Our response highlights how proposed copyright changes (Option 3) would negatively impact the creative sector and suggests preferable arrangements (Option 0 with additional considerations) which will better protect the intellectual property rights, business development, and careers of creative enterprises and practitioners.

¹³ <https://www.gov.uk/government/consultations/copyright-and-artificial-intelligence>

¹⁴ <https://ipoconsultations.citizenspace.com/ipo/consultation-on-copyright-and-ai/>

Table of Contents

Consultation Response	6
4. Do you agree that option 3 - a data mining exception which allows right holders to reserve their rights, supported by transparency measures - is most likely to meet the objectives set out above?	6
5. Which option do you prefer and why?	6
6. Do you support the introduction of an exception along the lines outlined in section C of the consultation?	9
8. If not, what other approach do you propose and how would that achieve the intended balance of objectives?	13
9. What influence, positive or negative, would the introduction of an exception along these lines have on you or your organisation? Please provide quantitative information where possible.	15
10. What action should a developer take when a reservation has been applied to a copy of a work?.....	16
11. What should be the legal consequences if a reservation is ignored?.....	17
12. Do you agree that rights should be reserved in machine-readable formats? Where possible, please indicate what you anticipate the cost of introducing and/or complying with a rights reservation in machine-readable format would be.....	17
16. Does current practice relating to the licensing of copyright works for AI training meet the needs of creators and performers?	17
18. Should measures be introduced to support licensing good practice?	18
19. Should the government have a role in encouraging collective licensing and/or data aggregation services?.....	18
20. If so, what role should it play?	18
21. Are you aware of any individuals or bodies with specific licensing needs that should be taken into account?.....	18
22. Do you agree that AI developers should disclose the sources of their training material?.....	19
23. If so, what level of granularity is sufficient and necessary for AI firms when providing transparency over the inputs to generative models?	19
24. What transparency should be required in relation to web crawlers?	20
25. What is a proportionate approach to ensuring appropriate transparency?	20
27. How can compliance with transparency requirements be encouraged, and does this require regulatory underpinning?.....	21

29. What steps can the government take to encourage AI developers to train their models in the UK and in accordance with UK law to ensure that the rights of right holders are respected?	22
30. To what extent does the copyright status of AI models trained outside the UK require clarification to ensure fairness for AI developers and right holders?	22
33. Does the existing data mining exception for non-commercial research remain fit for purpose?	23
34. Should copyright rules relating to AI consider factors such as the purpose of an AI model, or the size of an AI firm?	23
39. Would reforming the CGW provision have an impact on you or your organisation? If so, how? Please provide quantitative information where possible.	24
42. Would the removal of the current CGW provision affect you or your organisation? Please provide quantitative information where possible.....	24
45. Do you agree that generative AI outputs should be labelled as AI generated? If so, what is a proportionate approach, and is regulation required?	24
47. What are your views on the EU's approach to AI output labelling?	25
48. To what extent would the approach(es) outlined in the first part of this consultation, in relation to transparency and text and data mining, provide individuals with sufficient control over the use of their image and voice in AI outputs?.....	25
50. Is the legal framework that applies to AI products that interact with copyright works at the point of inference clear? If it is not, what could the government do to make it clearer?	26
Appendix: Full Consultation Questions.....	27

Consultation Response

4. Do you agree that option 3 - a data mining exception which allows right holders to reserve their rights, supported by transparency measures - is most likely to meet the objectives set out above?

No.

Whilst we see enormous potential benefits of regulatory requirements around transparency of AI, as noted in our response to later questions on this topic, we do not agree that the data mining exception and reservation of rights is an appropriate or workable prospect, as outlined in detail in our response to question 5.

5. Which option do you prefer and why?

Option 0: Copyright and related laws remain as they are

Option 0 is preferred of these options as the least harmful to the creative industries that will still enable flexibility for both those originating creative content, and for those who wish to innovate with AI – including creative innovators who are themselves creating new AI models. However, our preference would be for a variant of Option 0 that included: (a) an overdue update of the Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1988 to ensure it was more appropriately suited to the post digital and post internet realities of Copyright, including some updates to licensing and platform norms; (b) introduction of the transparency measures outlined for Option 3, which we see as very valuable in the context of AI; measures to support explicitly permitted use of copyright work for AI training under license (paid for or free), which we suggest would be best supported by an opt in registry.

Option 1, whilst appealing, includes some practical challenges, largely because of the complexity of how AI models are developed and trained, which means that new models will almost always have their origins in code elements from previous models or approaches, so fully and retrospectively applying licensing, and doing so internationally, would be impractical. However, the principle that content used for training should be appropriately licensed (whether that is through payment or other forms or partnership or permissioning, including open licenses), is correct.

Option 2 provides little benefit for creative people and organisations generating new copyright and IP – as noted in the Annex – Summary of Options supplied with this consultation.

The government's preferred Option 3 favours AI developers' rights significantly over the rights of copyright creators. Option 3 is also entirely dependent on the existence of a reliable and practical rights reservation mechanism, despite there being no standard approach for implementing these, and only a few proprietary examples cited in the consultation paper. The use of a rights reservation mechanism is deeply problematic as it:

(a) places all of the burden on creators to disclose their IP as it arises – with no clarity over whether they must register every item individually or whether a full body of work may be registered at once. (Although we would anticipate that to enable machine readability of this information, a relatively high granularity of information and a high quality of consistent and structured data would be required, placing particularly high burden on small businesses and sole traders.) It is also unclear how such a rights reservation mechanism would function in the case of more complex shared copyright cases where creators may not agree about the potential use of their work as training data, or where the copyright and moral rights do not all sit with one rights holder (not uncommon particularly in some forms of creative work, e.g. film production). It also misunderstands the complexities of copyright law, particularly in tracing the holders of copyright, given the number of “orphan works” materials where the copyright holder is not known or untraceable.

(b) requires the copyright holder to directly tell the body operating the rights reservation mechanism where to find their content, in the hope that this will be managed in a trustworthy way and used responsibly. However, we note that the current operators of comparable systems are commercial AI development companies with little regulating their use of such data. We also note that any such look up could be as easily used for malicious as well as appropriate reference use.

(c) any such mechanism depends on its operator maintaining the mechanism and doing so under the appropriate terms and values it has been established under. If commercially operated, these may be at risk of market forces, for instance the recent shifts at OpenAI from not for profit to a for-profit "public benefits corporation" announced in 2024 shows the speed at which such conditions can change – with moves to "for profit" models, for instance, inherently changing priorities. However, even if integrity is maintained, the operator will need to have longevity, resilience and independence to operate appropriately. If Option 3 were to go forward the UK Government would have to take exceptional care to ensure a rights reservation mechanism would genuinely protect creative work. To do so it would need to sit with an independent, well-funded, long-term (in line with copyright protections) and independent organisation, with appropriate governance structure and accountability to regulators. Furthermore, there would need to be a way for creators to be able register their work as a body of work– encompassing current, past and future IP – rather than having to provide detail on every item that is to be included in an opt out. This would

make such a mechanism more feasible for creatives, though it would be more complex to manage automatically and would require significant ongoing resourcing for the rights reservation mechanism. However, there is only scant detail of how this rights reservation model might work in practice in the proposal, it being a crucial underpinning assumption of Option 3. It is also worth noting that previous UK government attempts to provide infrastructure for copyright management, namely the Orphan Works Licensing Scheme, has not been a success. ([See https://olh.openlibhums.org/article/id/4573/](https://olh.openlibhums.org/article/id/4573/))

Option 3 stakes the perceived benefits of generative AI against the existing impact of the creative industries. However, the impact of the creative industries on the UK economy is extremely substantial, and the financial model for creatives' livelihoods and businesses generating £124.8 billion GVA for the UK economy (noted in the Executive Summary of this consultation, paragraph 3) is enmeshed in copyright law and royalty models. Investment in the creative industries is growing in terms of private investors and allows for growth and scaling internationally. Underpinning their value to investors is their assets – their intellectual assets, as well as their ability to exploit their assets. Replicated or extrapolated generative AI output, created without permission or reward, is Copyright infringement and there have been long standing legal precedents that have reinforced that position music, fashion, TV formats, film production, photography, publishing, and in the tech sector itself.

This consultation, and particularly the proposals reflected in Option 3, also choose to focus only generative AI trained on web scale data to train general models. However, we do not think this shows any understanding of the diversity of AI that exists and is in productive use, including in the creative industries, without relying on large scale copyright theft. Generative AI and general models use large volumes of data, and have significant energy and carbon impacts, because they are not trained in any specialised way. The largest global players in this space are already well established, heavily funded, and arguably overvalued when compared to their income. However, many of the most exciting uses of AI come from more specialist models trained on specific data sets, which may include out of copyright works (as we see in AI applications spinning into commercial companies with origins in humanities research), or permissioned use of specialist data sets (as we see in many of the medical applications of AI). There are also emerging AI companies undertaking new creative AI concepts that are built on paid licensing, and/or revenue sharing models with those whose training data they use under explicit permission (for example DataMind Audio (<https://datamindaudio.ai/>), based in Applecross, Scotland).

Rather than replicating the business models of general model generative AI players that are currently fighting numerous legal cases across the globe regarding their use of content without permission or payment, there is a real opportunity to mark the UK as taking a different position on AI and copyright. The next world-leading innovations with

AI will present something different, and business models that respect, compensate, and thus enable the thriving of the creative industries as part of ethical permissioned training data models (which can still operate at scale), would show immense leadership. The opportunities for growth of such models will also benefit from support of not only the AI developers but also the creative copyright holders who have contributed to their products and services; by using training AI under more appropriate opt in and/or licensing scenarios they will also limit their exposure to legal risk; and by ensuring rights are negotiated or paid for, they will not be easily replicated as products or may benefit from exclusivity of access to specific training data that gives them a global competitive advantage.

The purpose of copyright legislation is to enable the creator of original work to use and commercially exploit their work – and to protect them from its exploitation or misappropriation by others. Option 3 directly contravenes this and we believe it would have a detrimental impact on (i) the production of new creative works – by starving the sector of compensation for their original work, and (ii) the sharing of creative work in any form of accessible digital format, for fear of content being used without permission but (under this proposed approach) within unpaid and unaccountable AI training use.

6. Do you support the introduction of an exception along the lines outlined in section C of the consultation?

No.

The introduction to this consultation notes the importance of both the Creative Industries and the emerging AI industry. If securing the future growth of both is truly at the heart of the Government's intentions, we believe that protecting copyright and routes to opt in to the use of copyright content in the training of AI must be the means to do that. We do not believe an opt out system provides adequate protection for the creative industries, particularly SMEs and sole traders which – as noted in this consultation – make up the majority of the creative industries. We do not see an opt out system as feasible to implement in a way that is fair to rights holders, particularly as it places an undue burden on creators to register their work, adding further unpaid labour for creatives who already face many substantial administrative burdens as small independent businesses. We believe it is right that the onus should be on AI developers to seek permissions to use data that be used to train their models thus the underpinnings of their products. We believe it appropriate that AI developers should, pay for access to training data where needed, in line with current copyright protections that ensure that copyright holders rights have agency in how their work is used and exploited. We see an opt out system as posing a serious threat to the livelihoods of creative workers, but particularly threatens to stifle the careers and voices of the artists,

writers, film makers, musicians, and creative entrepreneurs of the future, including those we train at our own institution, Edinburgh College of Art.

The Theory of Change in the Annex: Summary Assessment of Options provided with this consultation suggests there would be: “better access to content and a clearer legal basis for training AI models, rights being more easily enforced, increases in licensing of content and lower transaction costs, with some new set-up costs”, but we do not believe this is a credible assumption. We are aware that research conducted by many creative industries bodies for the current consultation, also shows clear evidence of lost revenues due to generative AI already, for instance The Association of Illustrators (2025) report that 32.4% of illustrators are already aware that they have lost work to AI alternatives. Meanwhile, current court cases around generative AI show that a theoretical beneficial increase of licensing fees for copyright content through its visibility or accessibility as a result of (non-licensed and non-compensated) AI training use, is not the reality of generative AI, and does not reflect the lived experience of creative content producers already finding their work used in training data sets.

Much of the narrative put forward by AI companies – and reflected in some elements of this consultation – frames training data as very minor elements in much larger data sets, implying that such systems do not compete with individual creative works, but that is disingenuous. Firstly, even a minor contribution to a larger training data set is a contribution – generative AI only functions when there is training data, which is generally human created content on which to base new output, and so the creators of that generative work through their contribution may be extremely numerous but they have all fed into the resultant output. AI does not generate any original work without training data: therefore its business model, and the acknowledgement of creative contribution, must reflect that – which is only possible with appropriate copyright protections.

Secondly, it is not always the case that the output is built on millions or even thousands of input creative works. Generative AI, prompted to create specific types of work, also generates outputs that are reflective of much smaller, sometimes singular, creators. This issue is particularly visible in the context of prompts to generate work “in the style of” a particular artist, maker, etc. where rather than an individual’s work being a single part of a data set of millions of items, their own (relatively small) body of work is used as the main source and mimicked in a way which would clearly both represent a potential threat to their capacity to commercially benefit from their own unique creative style and ways of making work, but also denies them agency in the topics, contexts, and potentially endorsements of products or politics that they would never permit their own creative work or creative voice to be applied to. The nature of this type of “in the style of” generative AI threat means it most significantly impacts individual artists, creators and SMEs, leading to loss of earnings, distress and collective efforts to resist data mining for AI training and mimicry (Hill 2023). The issue is increasingly well documented in active

court cases against generative ai companies (e.g. Authors Guild v. OpenAI Inc. (1:23-cv-08292), see Ridgway, Fairen and Sim (2024)) and, for example, in The Authors Guild (2023) in their response to the US Copyright Office's 2023-2025 Artificial Intelligence Study. In that response The Author's Guild also note that, whilst not automatically protected by restrictions in current (US) Copyright law, "such outputs in many cases will nevertheless harm the potential market for or the value of the work, as well as the public's interest in incentivizing the creation of new works."

Scraping available online content for commercial purposes without permission is theft. Copyright is a RIGHT upheld in law. The Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1998 currently ensures that:

"The owner of the copyright in a work of any description has the exclusive right to do the acts specified in Chapter II as the acts restricted by the copyright in a work of that description." (Chapter I, section 2)

Chapter II clearly sets out that copyright grants the holder the *exclusive* right to copy the work, issue copies of the work, rent or lend the work, perform or show the work, communicate the work, to adapt the work. And that:

"Copyright in a work is infringed by a person who without the licence of the copyright owner does, or authorises another to do, any of the acts restricted by the copyright."

This applies whether it is the work in whole or in part, and that "it is immaterial whether any intervening acts themselves infringe copyright." And, when amendments were made in 2003, we note that terms were explicitly added to protect against reverse engineering of software – a protection which AI businesses directly benefit from themselves as originators or contributors to AI models and software delivering AI services and products.

The preferred option (Option 3) thus undermines the explicit purpose of Copyright – to enable the originator of creative work to benefit from its commercial exploitation and/or to have the agency to give or refuse permission over its use (whilst their copyright persists). The preferred option instead favours one particular type of AI businesses – generative AI and specifically generative AI built on general rather than specialist models (which often require smaller and more identifiable and feasible to license datasets). The preferred option thus enables these AI businesses to benefit from the commercial exploitation of decades of creative work owned by millions of creatives, without any compensation or recognition returning to those creatives, and without those creatives having any voice in the use of their work. This would be understood as a clear case of Copyright theft under the current law. If the business models of emerging AI businesses do not enable them to license or gain explicit permission for the content

they wish to use to train their models, it could be argued that they do not have a functional business model at all.

We instead urge you to look at the much wider AI landscape and the opportunities for growth of both the creative and AI sectors through much more innovative AI models that make more focused and efficient use of permissioned and/or licensed data, that enable benefit to flow back to those whose original creative work trains and powers AI models whilst still embracing many of the creative as well as benefits around efficiency that AI affords. In our own research with the Scottish creative industries in 2023 (Black et al 2024) we found genuine enthusiasm from creatives to innovate with AI in new creative models, but to do so in a way that values creative contribution and respects copyright and the value of creative labour.

References

Association of Illustrators (2025) UK Illustrators draw the line: AOI Publishes AI Survey Results. AOI website, 21 February 2025. <https://theaoi.com/news/the-aoi-ai-survey-results>

Black, S. R., Bilbao, S., Moruzzi, C., Osborne, N., Terras, M., & Zeller, F. (2024). The Future of Creativity and AI: Views from the Scottish Creative Industries. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10805253>

Hill, K. This Tool could protect artists from A.I.-generated art that steals their style. New York Times, 17 February 2023. <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/02/13/technology/ai-art-generator-lensa-stable-diffusion.html>

Ridgway, B., Fairen, Z. And Sim, A. (2024) Judge denies plaintiffs' effort to intervene in New York copyright actions against OpenAI. Reuters, 17 April 2024. <https://www.reuters.com/legal/legalindustry/judge-denies-plaintiffs-effort-intervene-new-york-copyright-actions-against-2024-04-17/>

The Authors Guild (2023) Comments of the Authors Guild: Artificial Intelligence and Copyright in response to the U.S. Copyright Office Artificial Intelligence Study (Docket No. 2023-6). The Authors Guild, 30 October 2023. <https://authorsguild.org/app/uploads/2023/10/Authors-Guild-Comments-AI-and-Copyright-October-30-2023.pdf>

8. If not, what other approach do you propose and how would that achieve the intended balance of objectives?

We believe, particularly given the uptake of open licensing models for some creative and technical works, that there will be creative copyright holders who are happy for their work to be used to train AI. This may include early adopters of the technology, those directly innovating creative use of AI, and those whose creative practice is not their main career or source of income. It may also include those from more diverse backgrounds keen to see better representation in training data sets. Additionally, there will be many creative professionals, SMEs, and copyright holders of all kinds who would be happy for some of their copyright work to be made available to train AI – so long as they could give express permissions over types of use made.

With all of the above, and the unworkable nature of a rights reservation mechanism in mind, we should suggest that rather than an opt out copyright process, a positive and thoughtful opt in system could be designed. This would provide a source of training data with clear permissions over the kinds of use that could be made of this data. Creatives would only grant those permissions at the point of adding their work to the registry – and could choose whether that permission was granted freely (or freely in some contexts) or whether by license fee. Some safeguards would be required to ensure the contributor, and the copyright holder of the works were the same, and to allow contributors to withdraw rights, if desired. However, such a system would provide to AI developers a current and in-copyright set of creative works and data. It would also allow creatives to participate in AI innovation going forward – including encouraging more trust in ethical models of AI which may boost adoption in creatives' own practices, or new AI innovations through the creative (not only the tech) sector.

Whilst we propose this opt in tactic as both a practical and ethical approach to making training data available, we would also note that choosing an opt out system that does not respect creatives' work could lead to an AI backlash from the entire sector and thwart AI innovation development in the areas related to creative content. We also note that properly licensed and high-quality data sets, including openly licensed data sets, are noted as some of the key recommendations around availability of data for training AI in the UK in the AI Opportunities Action plan (Clifford 2025) – and that this recommendation sits alongside other infrastructure and investment priorities as being key for stimulating growth. What is also missing from these plans is liaising with the library sector, who have vast swathes of digitised content, to build upon our already digitised content with potential for licensing revenue flowing back to support library and GLAM infrastructure.

In considering other alternative options, we would further note that AI developers, and especially AI SMEs in the UK can be developing any number of products that do not look

like the type of general model generative AI focused on in this proposal. AI SME's future work will include AI trained on properly obtained and permissioned data (especially in more specialist application areas where they are more likely to have first mover advantage), but also refinement of existing models, application of existing technologies, and development of niche fundamental research into new products - where training data will likely also be far more specific. We would also note the existence of large collections of existing openly licensed data which can be used in the training of AI, and the potential to license large scale data or partner with data providers (as already happens). There are also opportunities to digitise paper records, such as health records, to provide unique access to longitudinal datasets, working in collaboration with institutions holding such content for use by future generations. Scraping the web is not the only model available here, as already noted. Investment and growth should follow ideas and businesses with the best potential - which is not always (or often) the market follower ("me too") ideas that many of the general model generative AI companies are currently pursuing. Whilst the implication of the proposed exception is that copyright restrictions are limiting AI growth in the UK, the consultation document itself notes that this does not seem to be the case, stating:

“The UK is among the leading AI nations. It has world-class research and talent with the third highest number of AI research paper contributions per capita in the world. The UK is at the forefront of innovation with the third most newly funded startups in the world between 2013 and 2022, as reported in the Global AI Index 2024 and the AI Index Report 2023” (B. Copyright and Artificial Intelligence, B.1 Background, paragraph 29)

Copyright does not, therefore, seem to be presenting a significant barrier to AI growth in the UK at present. Both the AI Opportunities Action Plan and the recent House of Lords (2024) report into AI and Creative Technology Scaling, instead pointed to other factors, including availability of investment, infrastructure capabilities. Both reports calling for an improved innovation ecosystem which, it is our belief, will be best served by respecting creative copyright and ensuring that in making the UK “makers not takers” of AI (Clifford, 2025), we remember that creative people and copyright holders are already the makers of new work, and must have agency in how we move forwards with AI.

References

Clifford, M. (2025) AI Opportunities Action Plan. Department for Science, Innovation and Technology. London: The Stationary Office. (CP 1241)

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/ai-opportunities-action-plan>

Parliament. House of Lords Communications and Digital Committee (2025). AI and creative technology scaleups: less talk, more action (HL 2024-2025 (71)). London: House of Lords.

<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld5901/ldselect/ldcomm/71/71.pdf>

9. What influence, positive or negative, would the introduction of an exception along these lines have on you or your organisation? Please provide quantitative information where possible.

The introduction of an exception along these lines would be of extreme concern to us and our organisation, Edinburgh College of Art, University of Edinburgh.

Our primary concern is for the students that we train, from undergraduate through to PhD, to be the creative leaders of tomorrow. For these students, creators and future leaders and innovators to have a creative career, they will need to know that their work can be protected from misuse, and that they will be able to choose when and how to commercialise it on their own terms. If their emerging work is already being mined and exploited without any consequence or recompense, they may already find their creative voice usurped by generative versions trained upon it. We are also immensely concerned that the stages of the creative career path that are most threatened by generative AI are those early stages where creative practices are developing, but where generative AI models may be able to compete with emerging skills and ideas. Great unique creative work and independent creative voices can take time and practice to develop, but creative workers have the same living costs as everyone else. If their earning capacity is impacted by an exception that permits use of their work – including generative AI tools that may pass off that work or engage in mimicry of styles or original works – we fear that many of the graduates we produce may find themselves unable to sustain careers in the sector, which would be a significant loss in terms of missed creative and innovation potential, but also missed revenues for the UK, and missed growth potential round new creative work.

We work closely with creative industries organisations in our research, and indeed many of our staff are members of the creative industries with practices and SMEs alongside their university roles. These changes will have direct impact on our creative industries collaborators livelihoods, which in turn will impact their capacity to undertake new creative work or to participate in collaborative research that generates genuine innovation for the sector and the UK economy. We are currently working on the CoSTAR Realtime Lab (<https://www.costarnetwork.co.uk/labs/realtimelab>), working with the film, TV and games industry to explore virtual production research and development. We are not opposed to the use of AI in the creative industries and CoSTAR Realtime Lab is a context in which we expect to see the use of (ethical, responsible, and trustworthy) AI to increase technical efficiencies. However, we are also profoundly aware of the negative impact that the kind of unfettered AI training use of copyright materials from across the screen industries, as proposed in this exception, could have on these industries. This includes deep concern in the film industry over the wholesale scraping of content, the risk of mimicry, deep fakes, misappropriation etc. – and the implicit approval such an exception would give these abuses of copyright - but it is also

about issues including the rights of performers over the use of their own image and performance, something highlighted in recent SAG-AFTRA contract disputes over AI voice duplication (resolved through informed consent licensing models – essentially a new business model around voice performance - see Berger (2024)).

One of our most recent large scale research programmes, Creative Informatics, generated an estimated £78.5m GVA through our investment in R&D projects led by creative SMEs (Terras et al 2024), including SMEs working with ethical and highly innovative AI models. However, our fear is that the core work that sustains such SMEs to be able to operate and pay their bills as they are developing the ideas that will become innovative new products, services and experiences, is the type of work which may be threatened (and is already being threatened) by generative AI. We believe this threat will be significantly amplified by an exception that explicitly allows their creative work to be used as training data for a variety of reasons including encouraging clients to feel able to develop prompts to explicitly copy work without consequence.

References

Berger, V. (2024) SAG-AFTRA's AI Deal: A \$5 Billion Gamble on the Future of Voice Acting. Forbes, 21 August 2024. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/virginieberger/2024/08/21/sag-aftras-ai-deal-a-5-billion-gamble-on-the-future-of-voice-acting/>

Terras, M., Osborne, N., McDonald, C., Henderson, D., Pirie, E., Tyndall, A., Sulaiman, Y., Smyth, M., Panneels, I., Speed, C., Bates, C., Black, S., Jones, V., Zeller, F., Murray, V., Dale Steyn, I., & Smythe, J. (2024). Creative Informatics Final Report (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12575157>

10. What action should a developer take when a reservation has been applied to a copy of a work?

We do not think that rights reservations are a good solution, as already noted. However, if it were to be implemented, when a developer encounters a work for which rights are reserved, they should cease to use or scrape it, which may require complex technical architecture if the content is replicated across different locations or data is being re-scraped and rechecked against the registry. Reserved work should not be used to train AI and should not be temporarily copied or retained to avoid the risk of its inclusion in a training data set. We would also caution that it is extremely difficult to delete data points from a model once they are ingested, and so removing content from a model should a copyright holder change their mind is next to impossible. This must be clearly acknowledged and considered as a significant risk of any opt out system.

11. What should be the legal consequences if a reservation is ignored?

There should be serious financial and legal consequences, fully in line with this action being a breach of copyright. Ideally such consequences would be overseen by a regulator as related areas of work are regulated through the ICO or Ofcom.

12. Do you agree that rights should be reserved in machine-readable formats? Where possible, please indicate what you anticipate the cost of introducing and/or complying with a rights reservation in machine-readable format would be.

In theory yes, but in practice very few copyright holders will be sufficiently well versed in data and metadata structures to be able to do this directly. If a rights reservation mechanism were to be instituted, it would need to be designed so that at least one method of registering content would allow manual submission through an accessible and human readable form or process - which can then be turned into structured machine readable formats – in order to enable individual rights holders to assert their legal rights to their own copyright.

These questions relate to section C.2 Technical standards of the Consultation on Copyright and Artificial Intelligence.

16. Does current practice relating to the licensing of copyright works for AI training meet the needs of creators and performers?

The current practice and legislation is not perfect, given the majority of the Copyright, Design and Patents Act 1988 originates in a pre-digital era of copyright, content formats, publication, distribution and creative industries business models and there is no doubt that further updates are now due, particularly in light of AI. However, under the current legislation, the use of copyright data without permission is a breach of copyright, and that position is well aligned with the rights of copyright holders. Enforcement of that legislation is certainly not keeping up with current technologies – but the fact that there are legal protections for copyright holders mean that even when data is scraped and used without permission at present (as is certainly taking place), that usage is not permitted, and the copyright holder has a right to challenge it. Removing that right would be enormously damaging to copyright holders and would erode faith in and the value of UK copyright legislation.

18. Should measures be introduced to support licensing good practice?

Yes, supporting best practices, particularly around complex areas that can support more robust, thriving, but also innovative and imaginative business models – as licensing can do – is always to be encouraged.

19. Should the government have a role in encouraging collective licensing and/or data aggregation services?

Yes

20. If so, what role should it play?

It would be appropriate for the government to play a role in data that is created through work that is itself funded by taxpayers through national and local government, through UKRI funding, etc.

It is also not inappropriate for government to show leadership by convening key figures who have the capacity to make changes around collective licensing and data aggregation if it makes sense both for their organisations, and for the UK.

It would be inappropriate for the UK government's position on licensing and data aggregation to support the needs of a narrow vision of the future AI industry over the UK's existing (and future) creative industries and creative technology entrepreneurs.

21. Are you aware of any individuals or bodies with specific licensing needs that should be taken into account?

Many different creative professionals will have specific needs associated with the types of content, formats, and licensing models used in their subsector. We know that many of the representative bodies for creatives in the UK are also responding to this consultation and we would therefore defer to their specific responses, simply noting that there are a diversity of working and trading contexts covered by the creative industries, and by those creating new copyright works, and that this must be **at least** as carefully considered in any decision making as the needs of the AI industry.

22. Do you agree that AI developers should disclose the sources of their training material?

Yes. This is a best practice in transparency that also lends significantly better credibility to the work resulting from those models. Additionally, such disclosures promote trust in the AI developers' work by potential clients, users, etc. as well, crucially, helping to allay any concerns investors may have around future exposures to legal challenge over the legitimacy of training data from which the system is derived.

23. If so, what level of granularity is sufficient and necessary for AI firms when providing transparency over the inputs to generative models?

What material has been used as input and whether it has been ingested appropriately. In order to understand this, and potentially take enforcement action, this would include:

1. Where the material has been obtained from – this is important for all types of enforcement and follow up and also has implications (depending on the content accessed) relating to the Data Protection 2028 and the Only Safety Act 2023.
2. Who the creator of that content is (if known/included in the data or metadata)
3. Copyright and/or licence status of the content ingested (e.g. has material been scraped from a page or resource that is labelled as openly licensed). If material has been obtained through specific permissions or licensing, this may be evidenced by contract, correspondence, etc.
4. When the content was ingested (to understand currency/retention).
5. How the content that has been ingested has been used (to understand context of use and any ethical implications, e.g. have a rights holders' photographic data been used to train facial recognition systems for use in warfare?)

Most of the above should be accessible from the source material itself and/or through metadata created or generated in the ingest process.

24. What transparency should be required in relation to web crawlers?

Context is the key issue in understanding appropriate and inappropriate use of web crawlers, and transparency is a key part of understanding the context of their use and abuse. Web crawlers are not always problematic, but they can be extremely inappropriate when deployed for data extraction at scale, both of copyrighted work and personally identifiable information.

For instance, Bormioli and Agosti (2024) outline productive use of web crawlers in democracy, investigative journalism and corporate accountability – usage we would agree are important for fundamental human rights and the exercise of democratic rights. Web crawlers are also used productively in academic and scientific research, in order to access and understanding specific and selective types of information at scale, usually where no other access is provided. However, web crawlers are also used extensively in commercial general AI systems, where scraping tends to be unselective, very large in scale, and the objective is entirely commercial rather than research (academic, journalistic, or into accountability).

Transparency around the use of web crawlers, and transparency in how web crawlers behave, what they are accessing, whether they are obeying do not crawl instructions (e.g. in robots.txt files) is helpful in determining whether practices are appropriate or not. Appropriate usage (if obeying do not crawl instructions) would include whether content is being indexed (e.g. for search engines). Less appropriate or inappropriate use might look like sites being fully scraped for commercial purposes without permission or licensing (e.g. for use in GenAI training). Bormioli and Agosti raise this issue not only in the context of copyright but also in the context of Data Protection – as web crawlers do not differentiate between personally identifiable information and other content, which is also a significant concern of the current and future waves of generative AI and its relationship to the owners of copyright materials, and/or data subjects.

References

Bormioli, A., and Agosti, C. 2024. The two sides of web scraping: When data collection becomes a double-edged sword. EDRi (European Digital Rights) Resource, 17 April 2024. <https://edri.org/our-work/the-two-sides-of-web-scraping-when-data-collection-becomes-a-double-edged-sword/>

25. What is a proportionate approach to ensuring appropriate transparency?

The EU has introduced transparency requirements in the AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence) and specifically requiring generative AI developers to disclose: (a) the content was generated by AI (b) the model to prevent it from generating illegal content (c) publishing summaries of

copyrighted data used for training. This feels like a realistic and appropriate level of disclosure for systems whose functionality depends on the ingest and use of large-scale training data. Having clear regulatory requirements of AI developers to at least this level of transparency, alongside more extensive best practice guidance, would be a proportionate approach to both requiring appropriate practice and encouraging the UK to be a home of best practice. Additionally alignment with EU requirements (which are gradually coming into force) will both allow UK AI companies to trade with the EU in compliance with their regulations, and for global AI companies to understand and better be able to ensure compliance with UK legislation (rather than withdrawing from the market, as has happened both when North American companies failed to comply with EU and UK GDPR/Data Protection requirements in 2018; and in 2024 when many small businesses ceased trading with/sales to Northern Ireland and the EU due to the requirement to have an agent in those locations under EU's General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR)).

Any regulatory requirements need to be drawn up with an awareness of other potential legislation that may apply to the scraping and ingest of AI training data as, whilst Copyright is extremely important, it is not the only legislative area that is impacted by automated ingest of large / web scale data. For instance, personal data will be included in this data (Data Protection Act 2018). Inappropriate and illegal images, including of children, may be included in this data (Online Safety Act 2023).

Additionally, if AI is being used to create systems that are subsequently accused of misrepresentation of specific people or groups - as has been well documented previously, e.g. by Crawford (2021) and O'Neil (2016) - there may also be issues associated with the diversity of material included (potentially including issues enforceable through the Equality Act 2010 and/or The Human Rights Act 1998).

References:

Crawford, K. (2021) Atlas of AI. New Haven, Connecticut: Yale University Press.

O'Neil, C. (2016) Weapons of Math Destruction: How Big Data Increases Inequality and Threatens Democracy. New York: Crown Publishing Group.

27. How can compliance with transparency requirements be encouraged, and does this require regulatory underpinning?

Yes, compliance with transparency requirements will require regulatory underpinning to ensure that there are consequences for non-compliance. However, promoting compliance as a best practice and trust marker may be the most productive way to drive adoption of transparency requirements. Where the sourcing of data is clear, then potential users/clients for those systems, any trading partners of the developers, and current or prospective investors will have significantly increased confidence in their

capacity to assess the trustworthiness and any legal or financial risks associated with the AI product/model that has been developed. Additionally, individuals whose data may be included in the training data will have the capacity to object and exercise their right to request the deletion of their data under the Data Protection Act.

There are existing legal requirements that already regulate the use of data and the distribution of data that are also significant in the context of transparency in AI systems, and any additional regulations around copyright and AI should make reference to and be complementary to these:

- the Data Protection 2018 – for which specific and significant financial and legal penalties are in place, regulated through the ICO (Information Commissioner’s Office)
- the Only Safety Act 2023 – again, for which specific and significant legal consequences have just come into force, regulated through OFCOM (the Office of Communications).

29. What steps can the government take to encourage AI developers to train their models in the UK and in accordance with UK law to ensure that the rights of right holders are respected?

The government should ensure that there are both carrot (incentives like funding or potentially particular form or extended support for tax credits or similar) and stick (legislative measures to take action against copyright infringement). Additionally, there will be a need, no matter which option is selected, for public education, training and support for rights holders to understand any changes being made, how they will be affected, how to exercise their rights over their own work – especially if opt out is to be adopted (though we strongly recommend against this).

30. To what extent does the copyright status of AI models trained outside the UK require clarification to ensure fairness for AI developers and right holders?

Ideally, we would regulate for the standards expected of AI systems in the UK. In practice public sector procurement is probably one of the most easily controlled ways to enforce standards – requiring any bidder to comply with UK requirements is already a standard element of such processes, and contracts tend to be of a scale that can help incentivise compliance.

It is also the case that better informing the public about AI models and functioning and supporting UK developers and rights holders to communicate where standards are followed and best practices embraced, will help raise the visibility of better AI systems. Rather than being a weakness of the UK relative to models trained elsewhere, there is an opportunity to see these more ethical models as a real asset and improvement.

One thing which will be hard to regulate – and one of the reasons Option 2 feels impractical – is where models (whether from the UK or overseas) are derived from other models and training data sets that would not meet the proposed standards. This is where transparency (suggested in Option 3 but we propose appending to Option 0) offers one possible solution – that UK AI developers would be obliged to handle data according to all current standards, but with an attendant requirement to disclose any other data dependencies, allowing users and clients to make a decision on the basis of risk, fairness, and exposure to potential issues when considering use of that AI tool or system.

33. Does the existing data mining exception for non-commercial research remain fit for purpose?

Yes, to an extent. It is increasingly the case that academic research works in collaboration with industry, which has the potential to cause some confusion regarding the “non-commercial” nature of the work, though in most cases the terms of collaboration agreements between academic and non-academic partners do provide sufficient clarity.

However, it is crucial for the advancement of the field – especially if we wish for the UK to (continue to) be a leader in AI and machine learning – that non-commercial research is still robustly supported in copyright legislation.

34. Should copyright rules relating to AI consider factors such as the purpose of an AI model, or the size of an AI firm?

Yes. For licensing all of these factors, and potentially also the industry and context of the use, play an important role in determining fair compensation. We also believe that the “purpose” element of this is particularly important for understanding the nature of any potential breach of copyright, the seriousness of that breach and its likely impact.

CGW (Computer Generated Works) Policy Option 0: No legal change, maintain the current provisions

These questions relate to section D.2 Policy options, of the Consultation on Copyright and Artificial Intelligence

CGW Policy Option 1: Reform the current protection to clarify its scope

These questions relate to section D.2 Policy options, of the Consultation on Copyright and Artificial Intelligence.

39. Would reforming the CGW provision have an impact on you or your organisation? If so, how? Please provide quantitative information where possible.

No impact

CGW Policy Option 2: Remove specific protection for CGWs

These questions relate to section D.2 Policy options, of the Consultation on Copyright and Artificial Intelligence.

42. Would the removal of the current CGW provision affect you or your organisation? Please provide quantitative information where possible

No effect

45. Do you agree that generative AI outputs should be labelled as AI generated? If so, what is a proportionate approach, and is regulation required?

Yes. The obvious approach to take would mirror the labelling of GM foods, introduced in the Genetically Modified Organisms (Traceability and Labelling) Regulations 2004 (in England with equivalent legislation in other parts of the UK), using simple clear language and information presentation to indicate that outputs have been AI generated or (as per the EU AI act) that the materials have been manipulated with AI (e.g. in a deep fake piece of work). Additionally, regulation would need to be in place that reflected accountability both for anyone not labelling data appropriately, but to third parties making use of labelled data, to ensure that labelling remains visible, accessible or usable in meaningful ways.

The best technical mechanism for this will likely lie in a piece of metadata that cannot be tampered with – the EU AI Act proposed a form of watermark and have provided

some guidance on this (European Union 2023), although exact technical solutions appear to remain in development. The Information Commissioner's Office also noted recommendations for this type of labelling as part of its response to its consultation series on generative AI (ICO 2024).

References

European Union (2023) Generative AI and Watermarking. European Parliament briefing. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/757583/EPRS_BRI\(2023\)757583_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/757583/EPRS_BRI(2023)757583_EN.pdf)

ICO (2024) Accuracy of training data and model outputs. In The Information Commissioner's Office response to the consultation series on generative AI. ICO website, December 2024. <https://ico.org.uk/about-the-ico/what-we-do/our-work-on-artificial-intelligence/response-to-the-consultation-series-on-generative-ai/accuracy-of-training-data-and-model-outputs/>

47. What are your views on the EU's approach to AI output labelling?

We support the labelling of AI outputs to ensure they are understood to be generated or manipulated by AI. Further thoughts are noted in answer to question 45.

48. To what extent would the approach(es) outlined in the first part of this consultation, in relation to transparency and text and data mining, provide individuals with sufficient control over the use of their image and voice in AI outputs?

We believe that protection of copyrighted works and any regulatory support for that protection of copyright holders rights, including transparency measures, are to be encouraged. We would note that an individual's image and voice include personally identifiable information and are therefore not only subject to Copyright (1988) legislation, but also Data Protection (2018) legislation, and in some cases the Equality Act (2010) – they may therefore require enhanced and/or differently structured transparency mechanism. The protection of individuals' own image, voice and other personally identifiable characteristics also represents a significant potential negative impact, if used to train AI. Those impacts are similar to issues raised earlier in this response regarding specific prompts to explicitly mimic individual creator's work or styles, but use of voice or image data and/or simulated voice and image data built on existing training data, has the potential to be particularly personally impactful for individuals depending on the use, and method of discovery of the outputs that show traces of such training data.

50. Is the legal framework that applies to AI products that interact with copyright works at the point of inference clear? If it is not, what could the government do to make it clearer?

No

There is scope for increased clarification, particularly if introducing new legislation around training data. We would also note that, depending on the technical implementation of the AI system, the point of inference may well enable a user to directly introduce a new copyright work to the system (likely breaching the copyright of that work in the process) which may act as a prompt or trigger to produce a mimic or deep fake of a copyright holders work. Clarity over copyright at this point of inference, particularly if triggered by a deliberate user prompt or interaction (rather than e.g. use of inference in an automated system encountering data through sensors), presents a high risk of triggering outputs that deliberately infringe on specific rights holders with a significant negative impact on the rights and income of that copyright holder.

Additionally, as noted elsewhere in this response, we do also think any Copyright and AI legislation or amendments to legislation should take account of the diversity of AI models and approaches, not only focus on general model generative AI – as this consultation largely does.

Appendix: Full Consultation Questions

1. What is your name?
2. What is your email address?
3. What is your organisation?
4. Do you agree that option 3 - a data mining exception which allows right holders to reserve their rights, supported by transparency measures - is most likely to meet the objectives set out above?
5. Which option do you prefer and why?
6. Do you support the introduction of an exception along the lines outlined in section C of the consultation?
7. If so, what aspects do you consider to be the most important?
8. If not, what other approach do you propose and how would that achieve the intended balance of objectives?
9. What influence, positive or negative, would the introduction of an exception along these lines have on you or your organisation? Please provide quantitative information where possible.
10. What action should a developer take when a reservation has been applied to a copy of a work?
11. What should be the legal consequences if a reservation is ignored?
12. Do you agree that rights should be reserved in machine-readable formats? Where possible, please indicate what you anticipate the cost of introducing and/or complying with a rights reservation in machine-readable format would be.
13. Is there a need for greater standardisation of rights reservation protocols?
14. How can compliance with standards be encouraged?
15. Should the government have a role in ensuring this and, if so, what should that be?
16. Does current practice relating to the licensing of copyright works for AI training meet the needs of creators and performers?
17. Where possible, please indicate the revenue/cost that you or your organisation receives/pays per year for this licensing under current practice.
18. Should measures be introduced to support licensing good practice?

19. Should the government have a role in encouraging collective licensing and/or data aggregation services?
20. If so, what role should it play?
21. Are you aware of any individuals or bodies with specific licensing needs that should be taken into account?
22. Do you agree that AI developers should disclose the sources of their training material?
23. If so, what level of granularity is sufficient and necessary for AI firms when providing transparency over the inputs to generative models?
24. What transparency should be required in relation to web crawlers?
25. What is a proportionate approach to ensuring appropriate transparency?
26. Where possible, please indicate what you anticipate the costs of introducing transparency measures on AI developers would be.
27. How can compliance with transparency requirements be encouraged, and does this require regulatory underpinning?
28. What are your views on the EU's approach to transparency?
29. What steps can the government take to encourage AI developers to train their models in the UK and in accordance with UK law to ensure that the rights of right holders are respected?
30. To what extent does the copyright status of AI models trained outside the UK require clarification to ensure fairness for AI developers and right holders?
31. Does the temporary copies exception require clarification in relation to AI training?
32. If so, how could this be done in a way that does not undermine the intended purpose of this exception?
33. Does the existing data mining exception for non-commercial research remain fit for purpose?
34. Should copyright rules relating to AI consider factors such as the purpose of an AI model, or the size of an AI firm?
35. Are you in favour of maintaining current protection for computer-generated works? If yes, please explain whether and how you currently rely on this provision.
36. Do you have views on how the provision should be interpreted?

37. Would CGW legislation benefit from greater legal clarity, for example to clarify the originality requirement? If so, how should it be clarified?
38. Should other changes be made to the scope of CGW protection?
39. Would reforming the CGW provision have an impact on you or your organisation? If so, how? Please provide quantitative information where possible.
40. Are you in favour of removing copyright protection for computer-generated works without a human author?
41. What would be the economic impact of doing this? Please provide quantitative information where possible.
42. Would the removal of the current CGW provision affect you or your organisation? Please provide quantitative information where possible
43. Does the current approach to liability in AI-generated outputs allow effective enforcement of copyright?
44. What steps should AI providers take to avoid copyright infringing outputs? Please give us your views
45. Do you agree that generative AI outputs should be labelled as AI generated? If so, what is a proportionate approach, and is regulation required?
46. How can government support development of emerging tools and standards, reflecting the technical challenges associated with labelling tools?
47. What are your views on the EU's approach to AI output labelling?
48. To what extent would the approach(es) outlined in the first part of this consultation, in relation to transparency and text and data mining, provide individuals with sufficient control over the use of their image and voice in AI outputs?
49. Could you share your experience or evidence of AI and digital replicas to date?
50. Is the legal framework that applies to AI products that interact with copyright works at the point of inference clear? If it is not, what could the government do to make it clearer?
51. What are the implications of the use of synthetic data to train AI models and how could this develop over time, and how should the government respond?
52. What other developments are driving emerging questions for the UK's copyright framework, and how should the government respond to them?

Cite as:

Osborne, N., Parkinson, C., Terras, M., and Cruz, J. (2025). Edinburgh College of Art, University of Edinburgh Response to the UK Government Intellectual Property Office Consultation: Copyright and Artificial Intelligence. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15002867>

This document, excluding cover image, is shared under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0) license. Do let us know if you find it useful in your own work: designinformatics@ed.ac.uk.

Cover credits:

Image credit: Chris Scott.

Cover image shows Ben Cantil of DataMind Audio performing under his stage name, Encanti, at the Creative Informatics Creative AI Demonstrator event '*Exploring the Potential for Creative AI Showcase*' held at Platform, Glasgow, on 28th November 2023.

THE UNIVERSITY *of* EDINBURGH
Edinburgh College of Art

THE UNIVERSITY
of EDINBURGH

EDINBURGH
INNOVATIONS